

OPTIMIZATION OF DISTRICT HEATING SYSTEMS BASED ON A LIFECYCLE COST ANALYSIS BY INTEGRATING NON-LINEAR PROGRAMMING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

District heating systems play a vital role in enhancing energy efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. This study introduces an algorithm for analyzing and expanding district heating systems, aimed at optimizing their design and providing a useful tool for system operators in planning future investments and network expansions. The algorithm is generalized for applicability to any system and employs the Newton-Raphson method to calculate pressure drops, flow velocities, and, consequently, heat losses in the pipes. Furthermore, in pipe network systems, it is crucial to maintain the flow velocities within a defined range to prevent issues such as noise, cavitation, and excessive heat losses. Consequently, the selection of pipe diameters can significantly impact the system's efficiency and the network's reliable operation. In addition, the importance of the insulation material and thickness and their effect is addressed in the efficiency of the system. The proposed analysis method is applied to a model of the Kungsbacka system in Sweden, a demonstration site for ENFLATE, a Horizon Europe project focused on decarbonisation and enhancing flexibility in the energy sector. Finally, an optimization algorithm is proposed for the minimization of the lifecycle costs, taking into account the piping diameters, the insulation material and thickness and their respective cost while respecting the required design constraints. The optimization process is performed using non-linear programming techniques and can be applied to determine the optimal district heating design for minimizing the lifecycle costs and increasing the efficiency of the network.

1 INTRODUCTION

District heating networks (DHNs) are an efficient and sustainable solution for urban energy supply, providing centralized heat distribution to residential, commercial, and industrial buildings (Romanchenko et al., 2018). Unlike conventional heating systems that rely on individual boilers or electric heaters, DHNs utilize a network of insulated pipes to deliver heat from a centralized energy source to end users and can integrate multiple heat sources, including combined heat and power (CHP) plants, renewable energy sources (such as geothermal, solar thermal, and biomass), and waste heat recovery from industrial processes (Tzouganakis et al., 2024). Consequently, the adoption of DHNs plays a crucial role in the transition towards decarbonized and energy-efficient urban environments.

Despite their numerous advantages, DHNs face several challenges in implementation and operation (Brown et al., 2022). High initial capital costs for infrastructure development, including pipeline installation and central plant construction, pose a significant barrier to their wider adoption. Additionally, integrating renewable energy sources and waste heat into existing networks requires sophisticated thermal management and demand balancing strategies. Regulatory and policy frameworks also play a crucial role in the successful deployment of DHNs, necessitating supportive measures such as subsidies, incentives, and carbon pricing mechanisms. Therefore, the optimal design and operation of DHNs constitutes an open field of research.

In literature several solutions that tackle different aspects of the problem are proposed. For example, (Wack et al., 2024) present an automated design approach that integrates scalable density-based topology optimization with a multi-period framework. By considering temporal variations in demand and supply, the methodology achieved a 17.9% reduction in costs and an increase in waste heat

share of 42.8 %. Also, (Blommaert et al., 2020) introduce an adjoint-based numerical optimization strategy for designing large-scale DHNs. Their approach reduces piping investment by 23%, demonstrating the importance of incorporating nonlinear models in network design. In a similar manner, (Wack et al., 2023) benchmark two approaches to non-linear topology optimization of DHNs: a mixed-integer non-linear optimization and a density-based approach. The study found that the combinatorial approach, which directly solves a mixed-integer nonlinear program, took 29 h to optimize a network for a neighborhood of about 600 streets, compared to 35 min for the density-based method. (Lasonder et al., 2024) have developed a reduced-order model of the heating network at Université Libre de Bruxelles to optimize its operation. By replacing fixed-speed pumps with optimally operated variable-speed pumps, the study achieved a reduction in pumping energy by up to 96%. Further optimization of network operating temperatures led to additional benefits, including a 99% reduction in pumping energy, a 19% decrease in heat losses, and a 7% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to the current operation. (Blizard et al., 2024) present a hierarchical optimization scheme that leverages user flexibility to improve DHN performance. By implementing this approach on a representative 20-user DHN, the study achieved a 67% reduction in bypass mass flow while ensuring all users maintained temperatures within 2°C of their desired setpoints. On a different, non-model-based approach, (Calikus et al., 2019) propose a data-driven method to analyze heat load patterns without prior knowledge. Applied to 1,222 buildings in Sweden, the approach identified representative patterns and detected anomalies, aiding in understanding customer heat usage behaviors. Following a similar, data driven, manner, the study of (Le-Coz et al., 2020) employs a data-driven deep reinforcement learning (DRL) approach to optimize the supply water temperature in Chinese DHNs, aiming to enhance thermal comfort and reduce energy costs. The researchers developed a recurrent neural network trained on simulated data to predict indoor temperatures, which was then used to train two DRL agents for optimal temperature control. In a multi-apartment setting, both agents achieved higher thermal comfort and reduced energy costs compared to an optimized baseline strategy. Specifically, the DRL approach resulted in around 7% reduction in energy consumption while maintaining indoor temperatures within the desired comfort range.

This study introduces an algorithm for analyzing and expanding district heating systems, aimed at optimizing their design and providing a useful tool for system operators in planning future investments and network expansions. The algorithm is generalized for applicability to any system and employs the Newton-Raphson method to calculate pressure drops, flow velocities, and, consequently, heat losses in the pipes. Furthermore, in pipe network systems, it is crucial to maintain the flow velocities within a defined range to prevent issues such as noise, cavitation, and excessive heat losses. Consequently, the selection of pipe diameters can significantly impact the system's efficiency and the network's reliable operation. In addition, the importance of the insulation material and thickness and their effect is addressed in the efficiency of the system. The proposed analysis method is applied to a model of the Kungsbacka system in Sweden, a demonstration site for ENFLATE, a Horizon Europe project. An optimization methodology is proposed for the minimization of the lifecycle costs, taking into account the piping diameters, the insulation material and thickness and their respective cost while respecting the required design constraints. The optimization process is performed using the genetic algorithm and can be applied to determine the optimal district heating design for minimizing the lifecycle costs and increasing the efficiency of the network.

2 Materials and Methods

In pipe network systems, it is essential to determine key parameters such as flow velocity and pressure drop across each pipe. Keeping the flow velocities within a specified range, between a minimum and maximum value, is crucial to prevent issues such as noise, cavitation, and excessive power losses. Additionally, calculating the pressure drop in each pipe is necessary to assess the mechanical losses in the network and to determine the required pump capacity for the system to operate smoothly. Generally, a pipe network can be quite complex, containing numerous pipes and nodes. The consumption requirements at each node (V_d) play a significant role in the network's operation, particularly if these requirements are time dependent.

The district heating problem can be viewed as a flow network problem when the energy demands at each node are treated as consumption requirements. However, in district heating systems, it is also

important to account for heat losses, as these can substantially impact the overall efficiency of the system.

2.1 Generalized Solution of the Pipe Network Problem

The pressure drop across a pipe can be calculated using the following formula, which accounts for the major losses resulting from friction between the fluid and the pipe walls:

$$\Delta P = K \cdot \dot{V}^2 \quad (1)$$

where (ΔP) is the pressure drop, (\dot{V}) is the volumetric flow rate and

$$K = \frac{8 \cdot \rho \cdot L \cdot f_d}{\pi^2 \cdot D^5} \quad (2)$$

where (ρ) is the fluid density, (L) the length of the pipe, (D) the inner diameter of the pipe and (f_d) is the linear losses coefficient that can be approximated from the following formula:

$$f_d = \left(\frac{1}{1.14 - 2 \log \left(\frac{\epsilon}{D} \right)} + \frac{21.25}{Re^{0.9}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

where (ϵ) is the roughness of the pipe surface and (Re) is the Reynolds that can be calculated from:

$$Re = \frac{4 \cdot \dot{V}}{\pi \cdot D \cdot \nu} \quad (4)$$

where (ν) is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid.

Thus, using Eq. (1)-(4), the pressure drop for a given pipe and flow rate can be determined, considering the major losses due to the viscous forces between the fluid and the pipe walls.

Consequently, the flow between two nodes, (i) and (j), can be calculated as follows:

$$\dot{V}_{ij} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{|P_i - P_j - \rho g \Delta h|}{K_{ij}} \right)} \quad (5)$$

where (\dot{V}_{ij}) is the flow rate at the pipe, (P_i) and (P_j) are the pressures at node (i) and (j) respectively, (g) is the acceleration of gravity, (Δh) is the height difference between node (i) and (j) and (K_{ij}) are the major losses of the pipe as obtained from Eq.(2). From Eq.(5) it yields that:

- If $P_i - P_j - \rho g \Delta h > 0$ then the flow is: $i \rightarrow j$
- If $P_i - P_j - \rho g \Delta h < 0$ then the flow is: $j \rightarrow i$

The Jacobian of the Eq.(5) is:

$$\frac{\partial \dot{V}_{ij}}{\partial P_i} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{K_{ij}}} \cdot \frac{1}{|P_i - P_j - \rho g \Delta h|^{1/2}} \quad (6.A)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{V}_{ij}}{\partial P_i} = -\frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{K_{ij}}} \cdot \frac{1}{|P_i - P_j - \rho g \Delta h|^{1/2}} \quad (6.B)$$

Since the pressure at each node of the system is unknown the Newton-Raphson algorithm will be implemented, as the system is nonlinear. Initially, the pressures (\mathbf{P}_{old}) at each node of the network will be assumed. Then, from Eq.(1)-(5) the flow rate and its direction at each pipe will be calculated, while Eq.(6) will be used to determine the Jacobian matrix (\mathbf{JAC}).

As a result, the sum(\mathbf{F}), of the flow rates (\dot{V}_{ij}) and the consumption requirements (V_d) can be calculated at each node. However, at each node the mass conservation should be satisfied ($\mathbf{F} = 0$). As a consequence, the new pressure at each node can be determined from:

$$\mathbf{F} + \mathbf{JAC} \cdot \mathbf{DP} = \mathbf{0} \quad (7.A)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{new} = \mathbf{P}_{old} + \mathbf{DP} \quad (7.B)$$

Eq.(7.A) is linear and can be solved using the Gauss algorithm. The newly calculated pressure at each node will then serve as the next assumption, and the process will be repeated until convergence is achieved ($\mathbf{DP} < \mathbf{error}$).

Thus, for a given pipe network, the flow rates and, consequently, the flow velocity (v_{ij}) in each pipe can be calculated as follows:

$$v_{ij} = \frac{4\dot{V}_{ij}}{\pi D_{ij}^2} \quad (8)$$

As stated earlier, it is crucial to maintain the flow velocity bounded between a minimum (v_{min}) and a maximum (v_{max}) velocity.

2.2 Temperature Profile and Heat Losses

The temperature profile of a fluid flowing through a pipe with a uniform temperature can be determined from a heat loss analysis. A simplified 1D pipe heat loss diagram is shown in Figure 1. In this case, the pipe is assumed to have a single layer of insulation, along with a protective steel casing to guard against corrosion and exposure to harsh conditions.

Figure 1: 1D pipe heat loss diagram.

As a result, for each pipe of the network the temperature profile ($T_{ij}(x)$) is calculated from:

$$T_{ij}(x) = T_{p,ij} + (T_{in,ij} - T_{p,ij})e^{-\frac{\pi \cdot D_{ij} \cdot h}{\rho \cdot c_p \cdot \dot{V}_{ij}} x} \quad (9)$$

where ($T_{in,ij}$) is the inlet temperature of the fluid in the pipe, ($T_{p,ij}$) is the inner wall temperature of each pipe (which is considered uniform along each pipe), (C_p) is the thermal capacity of the fluid and (h) is the thermal convection coefficient that can be obtain from:

$$h = \frac{k \cdot Nu}{D_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

where (k) is the thermal conductivity of the fluid and (Nu) is the Nusselt number that can be approximated from:

$$Nu = 3.66 + \frac{0.065 \cdot \frac{D_{ij}}{L_{ij}} \cdot Re \cdot Pr}{1 + \left(0.04 \cdot \frac{D}{L_{ij}} \cdot Re \cdot Pr\right)^{2/3}} \quad (11)$$

where (Pr) is the Prandtl number of the fluid.

As a consequence, the heat loss in the pipe can be calculated from:

$$Q_{ij,loss} = \rho \cdot \dot{V}_{ij} \cdot C_p \cdot (T_{in,ij} - T_{ij}(L_{ij})) \quad (12)$$

where ($Q_{ij,loss}$) is the heat loss at the pipe and ($T_{ij}(L_{ij})$) is the temperature of the fluid at the end of the pipe that can obtained from Eq.(9).

An important parameter that has not yet been introduced is the inner wall temperature of each pipe. Assuming that the temperature of the flow within the pipe has reached the steady state, the heat losses calculated from Eq.(12) should be equal to the heat losses from the pipe to the ground.

Therefore, the heat losses are equal to:

$$Q_{ij,loss} = 2\pi \cdot L_{ij} \frac{T_{p,ij} - T_{gr}}{\frac{1}{k_p} \ln\left(\frac{D_{ij,out}}{D_{ij}}\right) + \frac{1}{k_{ins}} \ln\left(\frac{D_{ij,ins}}{D_{ij,out}}\right) + \frac{1}{k_p} \ln\left(\frac{D_{ij,pr}}{D_{ij,ins}}\right)} \quad (13)$$

where (k_{ins}) and (k_p) is the thermal conductivity of the insulation and the flow and protection pipe respectively, (T_{gr}) is the ground temperature while ($D_{ij,out}$), ($D_{ij,ins}$) and ($D_{ij,pr}$) is the outer diameter of the flow pipe the insulation diameter and protection pipe respectively.

As a result, the heat losses at each pipe can be determined numerically from Eqs.(9)-(13).

2.3 Insulation Thickness and Material Optimization for Total Network Loss Reduction

Optimizing a district heating network to minimize total losses can be highly beneficial for the industry, leading to both energy and cost savings. One crucial factor, which will be examined in this study for its impact on total network losses, is the selection of insulation thickness and material for the pipes. Additionally, an important parameter is the inner diameter of the flow pipe, due to its discretization in order to accommodate standard manufactured pipes. Table 1 presents the nominal inner and outer diameters of standard pipes used for the flow pipes. For the protection pipe, an 8 mm thickness of carbon steel will be considered.

Table 1: Standard Diameters of Pipes

Inner [mm]	20	25.6	32	40.2	50.8	60.6	72.6	89	101	113.2	129.6	145.8
Outer [mm]	25	32	40	50	63	75	90	110	125	140	160	180

Table 2 presents various insulation and protection materials commonly used, along with additional details on their thermal conductivity and cost.

Table 2: Insulation and protection pipe Materials & Characteristics

Material	Thermal Conductivity [W/m/K]	Cost [EUR/m ² /m]	Low Flammability
Polyurethane foam	0.02	286	No
Mineral Wool	0.06	60	Yes
Foam Concrete	0.05	100	Yes
Carbon Steel	45	4300	Yes

It is clear that increasing the insulation thickness results in lower heat losses and improved thermal efficiency of the network. However, it is crucial to select the optimal material and insulation thickness by considering their associated costs. Therefore, the optimization will be performed to determine the ideal insulation material and thickness based on the lifecycle cost.

The life cycle cost (LCC) is calculated from as follows:

$$LCC = CAPEX + \sum_{t=1}^y \frac{OPEX}{(1+r)^t} \quad (14)$$

where (CAPEX) is the initial capital expenditure, (OPEX) is the annual operational expenditure at year (t), (r) is the discount ratio to account for the time value of money and (y) is the project lifecycle.

The CAPEX values are determined as a function of the insulation, flow and protection pipe and excavation costs as follows:

$$CAPEX = CAPEX_p + CAPEX_{pr} + CAPEX_{ins} + CAPEX_{exc} \quad (15.A)$$

where $CAPEX_p$, $CAPEX_{pr}$, $CAPEX_{ins}$ and $CAPEX_{exc}$ are the initial expenditure of the flow pipe, protection pipe, insulation and soil excavation respectively that can be determined from:

$$CAPEX_p = \sum \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot (D_{ij,out}^2 - D_{ij}^2) \cdot L_{ij} \cdot I_p \quad (15.B)$$

$$CAPEX_{pr} = \sum \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot (D_{ij,pr}^2 - D_{ij,ins}^2) \cdot L_{ij} \cdot I_{pr} \quad (15.C)$$

$$CAPEX_{ins} = \sum \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot (D_{ij,ins}^2 - D_{ij,out}^2) \cdot L_{ij} \cdot I_{ins} \quad (15.D)$$

$$CAPEX_{exc} = \sum \frac{D_{ij,pr}^2}{2} L_{ij} \cdot I_{exc} \quad (15.E)$$

where I_{ins} , I_p , I_{pr} and I_{exc} are the insulation, flow pipe, protection pipe and soil excavation cost respectively.

Finally, the OPEX is calculated as the savings in fuel consumption. Improved insulation of the pipes leads to reduced heat losses, which in turn lowers fuel costs for the district heating network. As a result, the OPEX cost is determined as follows:

$$OPEX \left[\frac{EUR}{h} \right] = Q_{ij,loss} \cdot I_{th} \quad (16)$$

where I_{th} is the thermal cost per MWh

The optimization problem outlined above is complex due to the discrete nature of the flow pipe diameters and insulation material. Specifically, it is an NP-complete problem, as it involves integer non-linear programming (INLP). As the total number of pipes and nodes increases, the optimization process becomes exponentially more difficult in terms of computational time. The non-linearity of the problem arises from the objective function in Eq. (14) (LCC minimization), as demonstrated by Eq. (9)-(13) and Eq. (14)- (16).

Two separate optimization processes will be implemented. The first optimization will determine the optimal flow pipes diameters that will yield the lower CAPEX cost (material and excavation cost) while respecting the velocity constraints. The minimum and maximum velocities are 0.15 m/s and 1.5 m/s respectively, according to similar studies in the literature. Since the problem is NP-complete the genetic algorithm will be used to obtain the optimal diameters that would result in the lowest CAPEX. A flowchart of the optimization process is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Flowchart for flow pipes diameter optimization process.

After the optimization process for minimizing the flow pipes initial CAPEX, a second optimization will follow to determine the optimal insulation material and thickness to reduce the lifecycle cost of the district heating network with the use of the genetic algorithm.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Flow pipes Optimization

The Kungsbacka district heating network located in Sweden, which is a demo site of the ENFLATE project has been used in the present study. A simplified version of the network is presented in Figure 3. Its topology includes a piping system that connect 24 nodes that represent a different neighbor in Kungsbacka. Node 1, denotes the start of the district heating network. In Table 3, some additional information regarding the average heat requirements and the required volumetric flow rates of each node, are presented according to the 1D diagram of Kungsbacka in Figure 3. In the Kungsbacka region the height difference between each node is small and therefore not taken into consideration.

Figure 3: 1D diagram of the nodes and connections in the Kungsbacka district heating network.

Table 3: Yearly average heat requirements and volumetric flow rates for each node in Kungsbacka district heating system.

Node	Q_{req} (MWh/year)	V_d (m ³ /h)
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0
4	0	0
5	481	9.71
6	60.1	1.21
7	0	0.00
8	817	16.50
9	443	8.95
10	410.6	8.29
11	329.7	6.66
12	0	0
13	0	0
14	139.7	2.82
15	27.5	0.56
16	42.4	0.86
17	465.8	9.41
18	163	3.29
19	91	1.84
20	44.8	0.90
21	40	0.81
22	17.8	0.36
23	51.5	1.04
24	14.9	0.30

A total number of 26 pipe lines are present and as a result the linear system that will be constructed, in order to calculate the pressure drop at each node and the flow velocity at each pipe, will have 26 equations. The surface roughness of the pipes is assumed to be 25 μm , while the inlet temperature of water at the starting point is 80°C and the ground temperature is 5°C. In Table 4, the details regarding the connections of the district heating network and the calculated optimal flow pipe diameters, following the optimization process shown in Figure 2, are presented along with the flow velocities and pressure drops. It can be observed that the flow velocity in all the pipes is lower than 1.5 m/s.

Table 4: Network connections, piping parameters and results.

From	To	Length (m)	$D_{ij}(\text{mm})$	$v(\text{m/s})$	DP(bar)
1	2	10	145.8	1.22	0.017
2	3	300	89	1.47	0.599
2	4	150	101	1.41	0.270
4	5	30	60.6	1.05	0.040
5	6	20	25.6	0.66	0.030
4	7	150	89	1.32	0.260
7	8	50	89	0.90	0.048
7	9	70	50.8	1.30	0.265
3	10	60	60.6	0.69	0.169
3	11	180	89	1.15	0.327
11	13	30	25.6	0.18	0.054
10	12	40	25.6	0.63	0.093
12	8	30	40.2	0.79	0.096
12	14	100	32	0.85	0.331
14	9	70	20	0.50	0.211
13	14	40	20	0.19	0.027
13	15	50	25.6	0.30	0.090
11	16	250	25.6	0.46	0.280
11	17	70	72.6	1.20	0.187
17	18	20	50.8	0.69	0.125
18	21	20	25.6	0.44	0.095
18	20	20	32	0.31	0.046
17	19	30	32	1.22	0.036
19	22	40	25.6	0.92	0.311
22	23	40	25.6	0.56	0.145
22	24	20	15.6	0.44	0.112

3.2 Insulation material and thickness optimization

In Table 5 some additional parameters, regarding the lifecycle cost objective function are presented according to similar studies in the literature.

Table 5: Lifecycle cost analysis parameters.

Parameter	Value
Network Lifecycle [years]	20
Annual Operational time [h]	8000
Discount ratio [%]	5
Thermal cost [EUR/MWh]	30
Excavation cost [EUR/m ² /m]	2000

In Table 6, the optimal diameters of insulation, in terms of lifecycle cost, for three different materials are presented. In addition, the heat losses at each pipe are shown.

Table 6: Optimized insulation in terms of lifecycle cost for different materials.

From	To	Mineral Wool		Foam Concrete		Polyurethane foam	
		$D_{ij,ins}$ (mm)	Q_{loss} (kW)	$D_{ij,ins}$ (mm)	Q_{loss} (kW)	$D_{ij,ins}$ (mm)	Q_{loss} (kW)
1	2	226.8	1.18	226.8	0.99	226.8	0.40
2	3	226.8	11.54	226.8	9.64	181.8	5.58
2	4	226.8	6.98	226.8	5.84	202.4	2.91
4	5	181.8	0.95	181.8	0.80	129.6	0.52
5	6	113.2	0.45	113.2	0.37	89	0.18
4	7	226.8	5.78	226.8	4.83	181.8	2.80
7	8	226.8	1.94	226.8	1.62	181.8	0.93
7	9	161.6	2.09	161.6	1.74	129.6	0.91
3	10	181.8	1.91	181.8	1.59	145.8	0.85
3	11	226.8	6.94	226.8	5.79	181.8	3.35
11	13	113.2	0.67	113.2	0.56	72.6	0.34
10	12	113.2	0.89	113.2	0.74	101	0.33
12	8	129.6	0.89	129.6	0.74	113.2	0.35
12	14	113.2	2.71	113.2	2.26	101	1.02
14	9	89	1.55	89	1.30	72.6	0.62
13	14	113.2	1.08	113.2	0.90	113.2	0.36
13	15	113.2	1.11	113.2	0.93	89	0.46
11	16	113.2	5.57	113.2	4.65	89	2.30
11	17	202.4	2.42	202.4	2.02	161.6	1.12
17	18	161.6	0.60	161.6	0.50	145.8	0.22
18	21	113.2	0.45	113.2	0.37	101	0.16
18	20	113.2	0.54	113.2	0.45	101	0.20
17	19	113.2	0.81	113.2	0.68	89	0.35
19	22	113.2	0.89	113.2	0.74	89	0.37
22	23	113.2	0.89	113.2	0.74	89	0.37
22	24	89	0.38	89	0.31	60.6	0.17

For the optimized insulation thickness in terms of lifecycle cost, the total heat losses for the case of mineral wool, foam concrete, and polyurethane foam are 61.21 kW, 51.10 kW, and 27.19 kW, respectively. This demonstrates a significant reduction in heat losses in the district heating network by using more effective insulation. The heat losses per unit length are 32.4 W/m, 27.0 W/m, and 14.4 W/m for the optimized network using mineral wool, foam concrete, and polyurethane foam respectively. These heat losses per unit length in the optimized network are consistent with other findings in the literature where heat loss minimization was investigated.

In Figure 4, the resulting CAPEX (flow pipes, insulation, protection pipe and excavation) and OPEX losses due to heat losses, are presented for the three insulations materials considered following the optimization process. It is evident that the polyurethane foam yield the lowest lifecycle costs. Furthermore, it is interesting to notice that for the optimized case, the CAPEX of polyurethane foam is lower compared to the other materials even if its cost is higher as shown in Table 2. This phenomenon is attributed to the fact that with better insulation the required thickness is smaller and therefore the excavation costs will also be lower.

Figure 4: Lifecycle cost breakdown for the optimal design of different insulation materials.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present work an algorithm for optimizing the selection of piping diameters and insulation material and thickness in district heating networks is introduced. The algorithm is generalized for applicability to any system and employs the Newton-Raphson method to calculate pressure drops, flow velocities, and, consequently, heat losses in the pipes. An optimization method aiming to reduce the CAPEX of the flow pipes, while respecting the flow velocities constraints, with the use of the genetic algorithm is proposed. In addition, the importance of the insulation material and thickness and their effect is addressed in the efficiency of the system. An optimization algorithm is proposed for the minimization of the lifecycle costs, taking into account the piping diameters, the insulation material and thickness and their respective cost while respecting the required design constraints. The proposed analysis method is applied to a model of the Kungsbacka system in Sweden, a demonstration site for ENFLATE which is a Horizon Europe project. Polyurethane foam yielded the lowest lifecycle cost, while the heat losses per unit length were at 14.4 W/m which is in accordance with other results in the literature.

NOMENCLATURE

Symbol	Description	Unit	Symbol	Description	Unit
CAPEX	Initial capital expenditure	[EUR]	Greek		
C_p	Specific heat at constant pressure	[J/kg/K]	ε	Roughness	[m]
D	Diameter	[m]	ν	Kinematic viscosity	[m ² /s]
f_d	Linear loss coefficient	-	ρ	Density	[kg/m ³]
g	Acceleration of gravity	[m/s ²]	Subscripts		
h	Thermal convection coefficient	[W/m ² /K]	exc	Excavation	
I	Cost	[EUR]	gr	Ground	
k	Thermal conductivity	[W/m/K]	i	Node i	
L	Length	[m]	in	Inner	
LCC	Lifecycle cost	[EUR]	ins	Insulation	
Nu	Nusselt number	-	j	Node j	
OPEX	Annual operational expenditure	[EUR]	loss	Loss	
P	Pressure	[bar]	p	Pipe	
Pr	Prandtl number	-	pr	Protection	
Q	Heat	[W]	req	Required	
r	Discount ratio	-			
Re	Reynolds number	-			
T	Temperature	[°C]			
\dot{V}	Volumetric flow rate	[m ³ /s]			
v	Flow velocity	[m/s]			

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